

Supporting Information to

Structure and Reactivity of the Ionic Liquid [C₁C₁Im][Tf₂N] on Cu(111)

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Figure: TOC

Figure S1. nc-AFM images of $[\text{C}_1\text{C}_1\text{Im}][\text{Tf}_2\text{N}]$ on Cu(111), deposited at 300 K, quickly cooled down and measured at 110 K. (left) Overview image ($1000 \times 1000 \text{ nm}^2$) showing IL islands of various shapes and sizes. The blue and black dots indicate IL-covered and IL-free area, respectively. (Middle) Close-up image ($100 \times 100 \text{ nm}^2$) of an ordered phase of differently oriented domains coexisting with a disordered phase incorporated in-between; boundaries are marked with dashed black lines. (Right) High-resolution image ($10 \times 10 \text{ nm}^2$) of the ordered phase, which is characterized by molecular rows, that is, stripes with almost a rectangular unit cell ($\gamma = 90 \pm 3^\circ$), with lattice vectors \vec{a} ($1.90 \pm 0.08 \text{ nm}$) and \vec{b} ($0.90 \pm 0.05 \text{ nm}$). For details of the phase and the structure, see text. All images were measured with $\Delta f = -400 \text{ Hz}$.

Figure S2. nc-AFM images, measured at 110 K after annealing an adsorbed IL adlayer of $[\text{C}_1\text{C}_1\text{Im}][\text{Tf}_2\text{N}]$ on Cu(111) at 250 K for 45 min. (left) Overview image ($1000 \times 1000 \text{ nm}^2$, $\Delta f = -400 \text{ Hz}$) shows IL islands of various shapes and sizes. The blue and black dots indicate IL-covered and IL-free area. (Middle) Close-up image ($100 \times 100 \text{ nm}^2$, $\Delta f = -600 \text{ Hz}$) depicting an ordered phase of two differently oriented domains with disordered species incorporated in-between; boundaries are marked with broken black lines. (Right) High-resolution image ($10 \times 10 \text{ nm}^2$, $\Delta f = -400 \text{ Hz}$) of the ordered phase, which is characterized by molecular rows, that is, stripes with a nearly rectangular unit cell ($\gamma = 90 \pm 3^\circ$) with lattice vectors \vec{a} ($1.90 \pm 0.08 \text{ nm}$) and \vec{b} ($0.90 \pm 0.05 \text{ nm}$), highlighted with broken black lines. For details of the phase and the structure, see manuscript.

Figure S3. Comparison of a series of nc-AFM overview images ($1000 \times 1000 \text{ nm}^2$, $\Delta f = -400 \text{ Hz}$) of $[\text{C}_1\text{C}_1\text{Im}][\text{Tf}_2\text{N}]$ on Cu(111) annealed at 200 K (top) and 300 K (bottom), measured at 110 K. The images clearly show the transformation upon heating, from only large and medium sized islands at 200 K to the coexistence of large and many very small islands at 300 K. High resolution images (Figure 1 in the manuscript) reveal that the large islands are ordered (stripe phase at 200 K, honeycomb phase at 300 K), while the very small islands are disordered (see Figure S4). For details, see manuscript.

Figure S4. High-resolution nc-AFM images ($10 \times 10 \text{ nm}^2$, $\Delta f = -500 \text{ Hz}$) of the small islands with disordered internal structure observed after annealing an adsorbed IL adlayer of $[\text{C}_1\text{C}_1\text{Im}][\text{Tf}_2\text{N}]$ on Cu(111). (Left) At 300 K for 1 h; these islands coexist with large hexagonal-type islands, see Figure 1b. (Middle) At 300 K for 16 h; these islands coexist with large honeycomb-type islands, see Figure 1c. (Right) At 350 K for 30 min; at this temperature, only small disordered islands exist on the surface, see Figure 1d. For details, see manuscript.

Figure S5. STM images of $[C_1C_1Im][Tf_2N]$ on Cu(111), deposited at <160 K and measured at 110 K (left); the overview image (top, $1000 \times 1000 \text{ nm}^2$, $U_{bias} = 2 \text{ V}$, $I_{set} = 0.5 \text{ nA}$) and the close-up image (bottom, $50 \times 50 \text{ nm}^2$, $U_{bias} = 2 \text{ V}$, $I_{set} = 1.0 \text{ nA}$) show IL islands of various shapes and sizes without long-range order. (Middle) acquired at 110 K after annealing the IL adlayer at 200 K for 15 min; the overview image (top, $1000 \times 1000 \text{ nm}^2$, $U_{bias} = 2 \text{ V}$, $I_{set} = 0.5 \text{ nA}$) also shows IL islands of various shapes and sizes; the close-up image (bottom, $50 \times 50 \text{ nm}^2$, $U_{bias} = 2 \text{ V}$, $I_{set} = 0.6 \text{ nA}$) reveals again the absence of an ordered phase. (Right) STM image acquired at 110 K after annealing the IL adlayer at 250 K for 15 min; the overview image (top, $1000 \times 1000 \text{ nm}^2$, $U_{bias} = 2 \text{ V}$, $I_{set} = 0.2 \text{ nA}$) also shows IL islands of various shapes and sizes, and the close-up image (bottom, $50 \times 50 \text{ nm}^2$, $U_{bias} = 2 \text{ V}$, $I_{set} = 0.6 \text{ nA}$) shows again only a disordered phase. In the overview images, the blue and black dots indicate IL-covered and IL-free areas. For details, see manuscript.

Figure S6. S 2p, C 1s, N 1s, O 1s and F 1s spectra of 0.3 ML [C₁C₁Im][Tf₂N] on Cu(111) from 200 to 360 K, along with the spectra for 4.6 ML obtained at 90 K as reference for the bulk IL (bottom). For each denoted temperature, a new layer were freshly prepared and measured under normal (0°) and grazing emission (80°; shown only for 200 K in blue). For a better visualization, the 4.6 ML spectra are scaled down by a factor of 0.2. Grey peaks indicate the signals of the intact IL, red peaks denote the peaks of the new species formed upon heating. In the C 1s spectra a small contamination of the surface was taken into account, as indicated exemplarily in the spectrum at 200 K; in the F 1s spectra, the overlapping Cu_{Auger} signal was subtracted (for more details, see experimental section and SI).

Table S1. Quantitative analysis of the composition of **0.3 ML** [C₁C₁Im][Tf₂N] on Cu(111) at different temperatures, as derived from the XP spectra shown in Figure S6 at 0° (and for 200 K also at 80°) emission angle. Also given are the results for 4.6 ML deposited at 90 K and measured under 0° emission as reference for the bulk IL. For quantification, the shifted (marked with asterisk) and the unshifted signals of the IL were combined to provide the total atom number for each element.

Temperature	S _{an, sum}	C _{an, sum}	C _{cat, sum}	N _{cat, sum}	N _{an, sum}	O _{an, sum}	F _{an, sum}	Σ
nominal	2	2	5	2	1	4	6	22
360 K	1.0	0.9	4.4	1.7	0.5	2.6	4.6	15.7
300 K, 1 day	1.7	1.9	5.1	2.1	1.0	3.7	6.5	21.4
300 K	1.7	1.9	5.1	1.6	1.0	3.7	7.1	22.0
275 K	1.8	1.7	4.7	1.7	1.0	3.6	7.4	22.0
200 K, 80°	1.9	2.2	3.9	1.7	0.9	3.4	7.9	22.0
200 K	1.8	1.9	4.6	1.8	1.3	3.9	7.3	22.0
90 K	1.8	2.0	4.6	2.0	1.0	4.2	6.4	22.0

Subtraction of Auger-LMM and contamination signals

On the (freshly cleaned) Cu(111) surface an Auger-LMM signal and additional small surface contaminations in the C 1s or O 1s region may occur. After film deposition these signals are damped and have to be subtracted for the quantitative analysis of the IL signals. The expected damping factor, I_d/I_0 , is calculated via the substrate Cu 2p_{3/2} damping by taking into account the different mean free pathes λ_{Cu2p} and $\lambda_{Aug/Cont}$ for Cu 2p_{3/2} photoelectrons and Auger electrons/contamination photoelectrons, respectively:

$$\frac{I_{d, Auger/cont.}}{I_{0, Auger/cont.}} = \left(\frac{I_{d, Cu 2p}}{I_{0, Cu 2p}} \right)^{\frac{\lambda_{Cu 2p}}{\lambda_{Auger/cont.}}}$$

Table S2. Binding energies and fit parameter fwhm used for fitting the different XPS peaks

Signal	S _{an}	S _{an} *	C _{an}	C _{an} *	C _{cat}	C _{cat} *	N _{cat}	N _{cat} *	N _{an}	N _{an} *	O _{an}	O _{an} *	F _{an}	F _{an} *
Binding Energy / eV	168.77	166.77	292.83	291.75	286.40	285.82	401.63	400.64	399.21	397.08	532.44	531.19	688.89	688.15
fwhm / eV	1.23		1.32		1.79		1.56		1.38		1.43		1.45	

Figure S7. S 2p, C 1s, N 1s, O 1s and F 1s spectra of 0.5 ML [C₁C₁Im][Tf₂N] on Cu(111) at 200 and 300 K; data from Figure 3, but at an enlarged scale. Grey peaks indicate the signals of the intact IL, red peaks denote the peaks of the new species formed upon heating. Vertical lines indicate the peak positions – see Table S2. In the C 1s spectra a small contamination of the surface was taken into account; in the F 1s spectra, the overlapping Cu_{Auger} signal was subtracted.

Figure S8. S 2p, C 1s, N 1s, O 1s and F 1s spectra of 0.5 ML [C₁C₁C₁Im][Tf₂N] on Cu(111) from 200 to 360 K, along with the spectra for 6.5 ML obtained at 90 K as reference for the bulk IL (bottom). The spectra have been measured for freshly prepared layers (for sample preparation see text) at the denoted temperatures under normal emission (0°). For better visualization, the 6.5 ML spectra are scaled down by a factor of 0.2. Grey peaks indicate the signals of the intact IL, red peaks denote the peaks of new species formed upon heating. In the C 1s spectra a small contamination of the surface was taken into account, as indicated exemplarily in the spectrum at 200 K. In the F 1s spectra, Cu_{Auger} peak was subtracted (for details see experimental section)

Table S3. Quantitative analysis of the composition of **0.5 ML** [C₁C₁C₁Im][Tf₂N] on Cu(111) at different temperatures, as derived from the XP spectra shown in Figure S7 at 0° emission angle. Also given are the data for 6.5 ML obtained at 90 K under 0° emission as reference for the bulk IL. For quantification, the shifted (marked with asterisk) and the unshifted signals of the IL were combined to provide the total atom number for each element.

Temperature	S _{an, sum}	C _{an, sum}	C _{cat, sum}	N _{cat, sum}	N _{an, sum}	O _{an, sum}	F _{an, sum}	Σ
nominal	2	2	6	2	1	4	6	23
360 K	0.9	1.1	4.0	1.6	0.4	1.8	3.3	13.2
300 K	1.7	1.9	5.8	2.3	1.0	3.4	6.9	23.0
200 K	1.7	2.1	5.7	1.9	0.9	3.8	6.9	23.0
90 K	1.9	1.9	5.7	2.1	1.0	4.1	6.2	23.0

Table S4. List of nc-AFM and STM images in Figure 1, and Figures S1 - S5, along with their operating conditions and File IDs.

Figures	Methods	nc-AFM set frequency Δf [Hz]	STM U_{bias} [V], I_{set} [nA]	File IDs [YYMMDD_##_##]
1a (L)	nc-AFM	-400 Hz		20201125_43_1
1a (M)	nc-AFM	-400 Hz		20201126_35_1
1a (R) / 5a (L)	nc-AFM	-400 Hz		20201126_27_3 to 27_11
1b (L)	nc-AFM	-400 Hz		20201130_83_1
1b (M)	nc-AFM	-500 Hz		20201130_52_1
1b (R)	nc-AFM	-400 Hz		20201130_73_1
1c (L)	nc-AFM	-500 Hz		20201201_42_2
1c (M)	nc-AFM	-500 Hz		20201201_47_1
1c (R) / 5a (R)	nc-AFM	-500 Hz		20201201_51_1 to 51_2
1d (L)	nc-AFM	-400 Hz		20210826_44_4
1d (M)	nc-AFM	-400 Hz		20210826_88_1
1d (R)	nc-AFM	-400 Hz		20210826_95_1
1e (L)	STM		2 V, 0.4 nA	20200901_35_1
1e (M)	STM		2 V, 0.4 nA	20200901_36_3
1e (R)	STM		2 V, 0.2 nA	20200831_65_1
S1 (L)	nc-AFM	-400 Hz		20201124_41_1
S1 (M)	nc-AFM	-400 Hz		20201124_95_1
S1 (R)	nc-AFM	-400 Hz		20201124_105_1
S2 (L)	nc-AFM	-400 Hz		20201126_59_2
S2 (M)	nc-AFM	-600 Hz		20201127_30_1
S2 (R)	nc-AFM	-400 Hz		20201126_190_1
S3 (L-T)	nc-AFM	-400 Hz		20201125_43_1
S3 (M-T)	nc-AFM	-400 Hz		20201126_6_1
S3 (R-T)	nc-AFM	-400 Hz		20201125_143_2
S3 (L-B)	nc-AFM	-400 Hz		20201127_75_1
S3 (M-B)	nc-AFM	-400 Hz		20201130_83_1
S3 (R-B)	nc-AFM	-400 Hz		20201201_73_1
S4 (L)	nc-AFM	-500 Hz		20201130_48_1
S4 (M)	nc-AFM	-500 Hz		20201201_38_1
S4 (R)	nc-AFM	-400 Hz		20210826_95_1
S5 (L-T)	STM		2 V, 0.5 nA	20200826_11_21
S5 (M-T)	STM		2 V, 0.5 nA	20200827_66_1
S5 (R-T)	STM		2 V, 0.2 nA	20200829_2_5
S5 (L-B)	STM		2 V, 1.0 nA	20200826_24_3
S5 (M-B)	STM		2 V, 0.6 nA	20200827_39_1
S5 (R-B)	STM		2 V, 0.6 nA	20200829_17_2

L = Left, M = Middle, R = Right, T = Top, and B = Bottom

Table S5. List of the preparation conditions and File IDs for the XP spectra in Figure 2, 3, 4, S6, S7 and S8.

Figure	Temperature	ID
2	275, 300 K	210512-05 & -08 210623-04 & -06 210804-03 & -04 210804-05 & -06 210908-05 & -07 210910-05 & -06 210930-05 & -07 211111-03 & -04 211118-05 & -06 211123-03 & -04 211215-01 & -02
	200 K	210831-04 & -06 210902-05 & -06 211025-05 & -06 211104-03 & -04
	90 K	210629-03 & -04 210707-04 & -05 210707-06 & -07 210707-08 & -09 210709-03 & -04 210709-05 & -06 210714-03 & -05 210714-06 & -07 210723-04 & -05 210723-06 & -07
3	360 K	210914-05
	300 K, 1 day	210923-01
	300 K	210907-04
	275 K	210928-07
	200 K, 80°	210902-06
	200 K	211112-03
	90 K	210705-05
4	84 K ↓ 800 K	210709-07 ↓ 210709-18
S6	360 K	211029-04
	300 K, 1 day	211130-01
	300 K	211110-04
	275 K	211117-03
	200 K, 80°	211104-04
	200 K	211029-03
	90 K	210705-05
S7	300 K	210907-04
	200 K	211112-03
S8	360 K	221004-04
	300 K	220923-04
	200 K	220918-04
	90 K	220921-05

Table S6: DFT results for the most stable structures; energies given in eV

	total energy	total disp energy	adsorption energy	adsorption energy “without disp”	disp adsorption energy	geometry
ion pair	-178.99	-0.67	-	-	-	IL_ref
anion	-87.62	-0.25	-	-	-	Anion_ref
cation	-90.08	-0.14	-	-	-	Cation_ref
surf 62	-462.58	-42.79	-	-	-	Surf62_ref
surf 82	-1295.13	-120.31	-	-	-	Surf82_ref
struct1 62	-825.01	-48.05	-3.51	-1.28	-2.24	struct62_1
struct2 62	-824.92	-48.03	-3.47	-1.24	-2.22	struct62_2
struct3 62	-824.88	-48.04	-3.45	-1.22	-2.23	struct62_3
struct4 62	-824.80	-48.11	-3.41	-1.14	-2.27	struct62_4
struct1 82	-2198.97	-130.71	-3.07	-1.38	-1.69	struct82_1
struct2 82	-2198.23	-130.30	-2.92	-1.31	-1.61	struct82_2

The entry ‘struct1 62’ in Table S6 refers to the stripe structure discussed in the main text. The entries ‘struct2 62’, ‘struct3 62’ and ‘struct4 62’ refer to other geometries representing local minima. The entry ‘struct1 82’ refers to the honeycomb structure in the main text. The entry ‘struct2 82’ refers to another geometry representing a local minimum.

Table S7: Decomposition of DFT energies in horizontal interactions present already in a freestanding IL layer and vertical interactions with the substrate emerging after placing the IL layer on the substrate; energies in eV. For a description of the considered stripe and honeycomb structure see text right after Table S6.

	total energy freestanding IL	total disp energy freestanding IL	horizontal interaction	vertical interaction	disp horizontal interaction	disp vertical interaction
struct1 62 (2 ion pairs)	-359.31	-1.77	-1.96	-1.56	-0.49	-1.74
struct1 82 (5 ion pairs)	-898.36	-4.63	-1.97	-1.10	-0.53	-1.15
struct2 82 (5 ion pairs)	-898.64	-4.53	-2.03	-0.89	-0.51	-1.09